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Abstract	This document is the output of T5.2 on Quality assurance. It contains the main activities performed on Data Quality, set up during the project and applied in the second acceleration period. It describes the methodology used, the template created, the validation and the analysis of the results
Keywords	Data Quality, Template, Data Quality Plan, Validation, Assessment, Data

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

D5.3 has the purpose to describe the activities performed by Task 5.2, during the ACTION project lifetime. It is addressed to an internal audience, but also to externals: other Citizen Science projects interested in analyzing their Data Quality issues, research communities, etc.

The information collected in this document are mainly related to the activities designed to support the accelerated pilots and to plan the Data Quality Assessment for each of them. Finally, the document also reports the analysis of the collected templates, with additional remarks and guidelines derived from the most important lessons learnt, to further support applications of the Data Quality Assessment plan in further Citizen Science projects.

In the last section, the document reports a session with a case study from a resident pilot, describing specifically how it managed its data quality process.

1 INTRODUCTION

Data Quality is one of the most important aspects to collect significant data in Citizen Science projects. Following a proper process guarantees usable information to support the purpose of the research.

In this document the overview of the activities performed during the ACTION project is presented, together with their analysis and the final considerations.

The next chapter of the document explains in detail the literature analyzed to plan the activities with pilots, the co-creation with accelerated pilots, the results achieved from this activity, and the methodology used. In the following chapter there is a complete description of the templates created for Data Quality Assurance for Citizen Science projects and how to complete them. In the fourth chapter the description of the validation procedure is presented (thanks also to the validation questionnaires filled by pilots managers), together with the results obtained from the Data Quality Assurance template.

Finally, the document presents a specific case study on a resident pilot focused on Data Quality procedures, and the final conclusions.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section includes the description of the literature analyzed to implement the activity on data quality assurance, and the preliminary activities with the accelerated pilots under the second round of the ACTION accelerator. All these preliminary steps were used to create the template presented in the next session.

2.1 Background and literature

In recent years, with the widespread use of monitoring devices and mobile phone applications, it has become easier to collect and generate a wide amount of data, especially from (groups of) private citizens concerned about health or environment related issues.

This is one of the enabling factors behind the proliferation of citizen science initiatives, aiming to generate evidence for national or local public agencies to intervene on a problem. However, quality, quantity and reliability of data collected in such initiatives are often hard to demonstrate, with consequent skepticism from authorities and potential failure of the citizen science projects.

Data “of a sufficient quality” is hard to define in absolute terms, as it is strongly dependent on context, nature, and type of data that is collected. However, as important decisions are taken based on available data on a given moment, it is of paramount importance to ensure the best possible quality of the data collected.

The EU Commission released in 2020 a Commission Staff Working Document on “Best Practices in Citizen Science for Environmental Monitoring” [EU 2020], which provides a specific recommendation related to data quality: “Recommendation 6: Promote the adoption, effective use and transparency of data management and sharing principles, methodologies and quality assurance/quality control in citizen science initiatives”.

In 2019, the USA Environmental Protection Agency [EPA 2019] released an handbook for citizen science initiatives, with specific templates for creating a Quality Assurance Project Plan (QAPP), which is a document that explains how organizations design quality assurance and quality control activities to ensure that the data they collect can be used for its intended purpose. The Handbook

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provides interesting templates in general, and in particular template #4 which encourages projects to define Data Quality Objectives (qualitative statements for quality) and to specify Data Quality Indicators (DQI), with related control activities and quality goals (i.e., levels/values for the indicators to discriminate between poor and acceptable quality).

Chiny et al. in their work [Chiny 2019] analyzed 12 different frameworks for the assessment of data quality, to provide an overview of these frameworks and to summarize and compare their main components including the data quality definition, assessment, and improvement processes. According to this study, the five main common dimensions are:

- **Completeness:** “The extent to which data is of sufficient breadth, depth and scope for the task at hand”.
- **Accuracy:** “The extent to which data are correct, reliable and certified”.
- **Timeliness:** “The extent to which the age of the data is appropriate for the task at hand”.
- **Consistency:** “The extent to which data are presented in the same format and compatible with previous data”.
- **Accessibility:** “The extent to which information is available, or easily and quickly retrievable”.

The same work presents also several other dimensions reported in 2 or more frameworks analyzed which might be important in specific contexts, and which are reported also in the tools presented in later sections.

As already explained, data quality is hard to define in general, as it is very dependent on the context, but it is even harder in many citizen science initiatives, for which the data collection process is often defined by willing citizens who are, however, not data scientists. One possible source of inspiration to produce helpful guidelines comes from the Ishikawa methodology [Ishikawa 1968], used in the industrial domain to detect and prevent product design and quality defects. More importantly, the methodology allows an investigation of the potential causes for products defects/low quality. Such methodology is commonly used in lean production and is also studied in the SixSigma Certification Program.

The methodology consists in the definition of an effect (in our case: poor data quality) and suggests creating a diagram with a branch with each potential cause of the effect under study. The final result looks very similar to a fishbone, and that’s why it is often called a Fishbone Diagram.

Figure 1: Fishbone Diagram

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To make sure that all the possible classes of causes the so-called “5Ms” were defined, to which a 6th M was added later. These 6Ms are the main branches (bones) of the diagram and are:

- Manpower (physical or knowledge work)
- Machine (equipment, technology)
- Material (includes raw material, consumables, and information)
- Method
- Measurement
- Mother nature (environment, the 6th M added later)

2.2 Interactive session on data quality with pilots

This paragraph describes the interactive session with Citizen Science pilots. The three sub-paragraphs describe the organization of the session, the execution, and the collected results.

2.2.1 Session organization

The interactive session was organized with the Citizen Science pilots involved in the second accelerator of the ACTION project, with a first overview on the motivation to collect data of a good quality, how data quality could be designed (which dimensions to be taken into account), the explanation of the activity, and the activity itself.

In the first introduction, it was explained that, with the advent of new technologies for environmental monitoring and tools for sharing information, citizens are more and more engaged in collecting environmental data, and many environmental agencies are using these data. A major challenge, however, is that data users, such as federal, state and local agencies, are sometimes skeptical about the quality of the data collected by citizen science organizations.

Data quality is dependent on context, nature, and type of data. The dimensions found in literature, divided in more and less recurrent, were presented to the pilots, to provide them a first overview.

After the introduction to the data quality, the interactive activities were explained highlighting:

Rationale: to understand prior knowledge, awareness and needs related to Data Quality, with a constructive discussion among the pilots with different perspectives.

Generation phase: pilots were provided with three questions and they had individual time to produce answers on (virtual) post-its. The three questions were:

- What is Data of a good quality in your pilot?
- Which are the main barriers you may/will encounter for the collection of Data with a good quality?
- What is the challenge of getting data of sufficient quality from citizen scientists' contribution?

Voting phase: post-its were then read jointly to identify possible shared answers and needs. Each participant had three votes to place on the post-its which s/he agreed with more.

Results: the needs of the pilots collected were used to provide better tailored tools and guidelines for improving data quality during the accelerator period.

2.2.2 Execution

The activity was executed by six pilots with the support of the Miro tool to make the session more interactive. The tool was explained with a small trial. The interactive part was divided with the following timing: 6 minutes to answer the questions with post-its (2 minutes for each question), 30 minutes with a round-table discussion with the presentations and explanations of the different post-its, 4 minutes for the prioritization (voting) of the post-its proposed by the other pilots.

In the following figure there is the board used for the activity, where each pilot is represented by a different post-it color, each star is the best preference vote from a pilot, while each bullet is a secondary preference.

Figure 2: Co-creation activity board

2.2.3 Results

As it is shown in the image above, for each question there are several replies from the different pilots. For the first question **“What is Data of a good quality in your pilot?”**, the transcription of the contents provided is reported below, starting from the most voted to the unvoted ones. In the right column a tentative classification with respect to the dimensions presented above is listed.

Completeness of the data collected (numerous indicators and parameters to classify better the information)	Completeness
Accurate information (accurate patterns of spatially referenced travel data via walking, cycling, etc.)	Accuracy
Comprehensive observation of the surrounding environment	Accuracy
The data is collected with continuity	Timeliness, completeness
Data collected by informed citizen scientists	Accuracy, precision
Sufficient level of detail	Completeness

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Corrected categorization of the data	Accuracy, free-of-error
The data is not affected by extraordinary events	Free-of-error
Precision of the data collected	Precision
Full coverage of the relevant area/problem	Completeness
Properly saved on digital way and required for specific purposes	Accessibility
Data need to be collected with a precise time and space order	Timeliness
Proper calibration of instruments	Accuracy

Table 1: Information collected to classify data of a good quality

From the information and votes collected, it is clear that **completeness** has an important role for most pilots: completeness of the data collected, continuity, sufficient level of detail and full coverage of a relevant area or problem. Also, **accuracy** has an important role in citizen science projects, highlighted in the need of accurate information, the comprehensive observation of the surrounding environment, the data collected by informed citizen scientists, the corrected categorization of data, and the proper calibration of the instruments. Other dimensions identified are: **timeliness** (data collected with continuity, and with a precise time and space order), **precision** (data collected by informed citizen scientists, and precision more in general), **free-of-error** (data are not affected by external events and are properly categorized), and **accessibility** (data are properly saved on digital way and required for specific purposes).

The second question asked to the participants was “**Which are the main barriers you may/will encounter for the collection of Data with a good quality?**”. Below the answers provided from pilots, where the firsts in the list are the most voted. In the right column, the participants are classified with one of the 6M from the fishbone diagram presented above.

The usage of technologies (even if basic)	Man
Time availability of participants	Man
Volunteers using relevant apps correctly	Man
Persistent data comparison	Method
Knowledge and perception of the volunteers	Man
Different competitive priorities for volunteers	Man
Incomplete information from volunteers	Man
No continuity in data collection (e.g. for time lack)	Man

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Errors during measurements (e.g. due to errors in sensors)	Machine, Measurements
Damaging or stealing of sensors	Mother nature/ environment
External activities that could interfere with sensors/data collection	Mother nature/ environment
Problem with covering all the areas	Method, man
Difficulties in task execution that request collaboration with experts	Method

Table 2: Information collected as potential barriers for data of a good quality

As it is possible to notice immediately from the table above, most of the causes are associated to **man** influence: usage of the technology, availability of participants, volunteers using relevant apps correctly, knowledge and perception of volunteers, different competitive priorities, incomplete information provided, no continuity in data collection, and the problem to cover all the areas. This means that all the activities to involve, recruit, train, and motivate participants are important in order to have data of a good quality. The second most frequent factor is **method**: persistent data comparison, problems on covering all the areas, and difficulties in task execution that request collaboration with experts. A good methodology is a solid base to start with the data collection, but it is also crucial to frequently analyze data to see if the quality can be affected by errors in methods that were not identified beforehand. **Mother nature/environment** refers to issues that are not easily controllable: damaging or stealing of sensors, external activities that could interfere with sensors/data collection. The pilots also mentioned the possibility of errors during measurements, which can be classified, depending on the nature of the errors, under **measurement** or **machine**.

Finally, the last question asked to pilots was “**What is the challenge of getting data of sufficient quality from citizen scientists’ contribution?**”. It was indeed expected that the “man” cause could be one of the most crucial for data quality, because in citizen science projects the effort from volunteers gives a huge contribution. Below in the table there is the information collected from the pilots during the interactive session. The replies collected from this question were labeled (in the right column) based on general actions to be taken to improve each specific aspect.

Guarantee sufficient training	Knowledge
Helping participants in prioritization	Knowledge
Explain to volunteers that additional level of details can help	Knowledge
Adequate quantity of volunteers	Quantity
Volunteers participate to more sessions, to make the sample more representative	Time
Fully understanding of the participants about what we are looking for	Knowledge

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Guarantee stable support to participants	Support
Signaling when the sensors are damaged	Knowledge
Safeguarding the sensors and download timing	Knowledge
Subjectivity: comparison to standard parameters is necessary	Comparison
Task execution: choose the right point to measure	Task creation/ execution

Table 3: Information collected as potential challenges in collecting data from citizens

Most of the answers could be related to the **knowledge** that is necessary to transfer to volunteers: sufficient training, helping participants in prioritization, explain additional levels of details, fully informing the participants about what we are looking for, signaling when sensors are damaged, and safeguarding the sensors and download timing. This means that with an adequate level of training and a clear guide on what to do, or easy self-explained tasks, volunteers are less prone to subjective interpretation, and actions can be improved and optimised in order to collect data with a good quality. Furthermore, the availability of volunteers is another important topic, which is expressed by two factors: **quantity** and **time**. Quantity is referred to the total number of volunteers available, while time represents how much time a volunteer can offer. If the same volunteer has time to perform data acquisitions repeatedly, the sample becomes more representative and the volunteer more skilled session after session. As the data acquisition is based mostly on volunteers, also the **comparison** is mentioned in the information collected, because it is necessary to check that data are not affected by subjectivity (comparison with standard parameters). Finally, a good process of **task creation and execution** is very helpful to collect data from the right places and in the right way. Some examples are: to create tasks ordered sorted by urgency, to cover all the areas and avoid having multiple acquisitions in the same place, to explain clearly the points where it is necessary to collect information, etc.

From this first experience with the pilots, it was possible to analyze the pilots' needs in terms of guidelines and supporting tools (templates) to define, monitor and improve data quality.

3 DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE TEMPLATE

The Data Quality Assurance template is a tool for Citizen Science projects. This chapter describes the purpose of the tool, the structure with details on the specific parts, and the explanation for projects to complete it.

3.1 Purpose of the template

The idea of a template to help Citizen Science projects to study the quality of their data was motivated by different reasons. A first one is that they need a general overview on how to monitor, manage and improve data quality, without being expert in that field. Furthermore, the needs of the different projects are very heterogeneous, thus it is important to provide a tool able to adapt to several conditions. Finally, the timing of such projects are often short and they need fast solutions to be applicable in the available time.

3.2 Template structure

The Data Quality Assurance template¹ is organized in three different parts: a first section providing guidance for identification of low-quality data causes, a second section supporting the creation of Data Quality Indicators (DQI), and a third section to support the definition of actions to be done to improve the data quality. For each one section, a table is provided, with a guide for the project manager to fill it.

3.2.1 Cause-effect diagram

A first table can be used for causes-effects analysis of low data quality, following the structure of the fishbone diagram. To analyze possible causes of bad quality in the data, the template starts from the question “what are the main variables that affect the low quality of my data?”. In the table, each column represents one of the “6Ms”: man, machine, material, method, mother nature, and measurement. For each of the M involved, a brief description with some examples is provided, in order to suggest possible interpretation of the characteristic.

In case in a Citizen Science initiative there is already a preliminary analysis of the possible causes, this step can be skipped as it is optional.

The operational and/or functional labor of people engaged	Facilities, systems, tools, and equipment employed, etc.	Raw materials, components, consumables used, etc.	Processes and services	Environmental uncontrollable and/or predictable events	Physical measurement, automatic sensor readings, and inspections
Man	Machine	Material	Method	Mother nature	Measurement
<i>Eg: volunteers training level, missing communication</i>	<i>Eg: devices</i>	<i>Eg: consumables needed for measures</i>	<i>Eg: training process, is your methodology based on scientific evidence?</i>	<i>Eg: weather conditions to collect data</i>	<i>Eg: subjective evaluation scales</i>

Table 4: Cause-effect table in DQA template

3.2.2 Data Quality Indicators

The second part of the template is focused on the Data Quality Indicators (DQI). There is a complete list of dimensions taken from literature, where the first five are the most relevant. The project manager has to select the relevant ones for his/her project. For each selected dimension, one or more quantifiable DQI needs to be defined. Furthermore, for each indicator at least one quality control activity (used to assess/evaluate/calculate the indicator), and a goal (which would define the minimum quality threshold acceptable for that indicator) have to be defined. The last column is dedicated to the most recent measure collected by the activity (or the best estimation of the status of the indicator), to see if the goal is satisfied or further actions are needed.

¹ Available here <https://zenodo.org/record/5059851#.YN68GegzZPY>

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Data Quality Indicators can be properly defined also considering the cause-effect table (e.g., “volunteers training level” listed above, inspires the indicator “Percentage of volunteers with a sufficient knowledge”, under the dimension “Consistency”, etc.). However, it is important to consider that not all the causes impact on Data Quality with the same weight: the analysis should try to address those causes which have the highest impact.

Data quality dimensions	Data Quality Indicators	Quality control activities and checks	DQI goal	Current/last quantification
Completeness	<i>Eg: Percentage of data coming from the different areas of the Region (north, south, east, west)</i>	<i>Eg: Monthly check of measurements locations</i>	<i>Eg: > 15% of data from each Region</i>	<i>Eg: 10% from south, 50% from north, 20% from east, 20% from west</i>
Accuracy	<i>Eg: Calibration vs measurements ratio</i>	<i>Eg: Periodic control of calibrations and measurements (monthly?)</i>	<i>Eg: > 80%</i>	<i>Eg: Only 75% of the measurements happens after a calibration</i>
Timeliness	<i>Eg: Percentage of sampling stations with latest data older than 2 weeks</i>	<i>Eg: periodic check of data coming from sampling stations</i>	<i>Eg: < 10%</i>	<i>Eg: 5% of the sampling stations do not have updated data</i>
Consistency	<i>Eg: Percentage of volunteers with a sufficient knowledge</i>	<i>Eg: Evaluation of volunteers' knowledge</i>	<i>Eg: 80%</i>	<i>Eg: 90% well executed the test</i>
Accessibility				

Table 5: Data Quality Indicators table in DQA template

Other dimensions listed in the table are: amount of data, believability, concise representation, consistent representation, currency, free-of-error, interpretability, objectivity, precision, relevance, reputation, security, understandability, validity, and value-added.

3.2.2 Improvement Activities

The following table is dedicated to the collection of improvement activities to increase data quality. The idea is to look at the actual measurements of the DQI, identify the DQI which miss their target and try to improve the results with dedicated actions. One activity might involve more than one DQI, as well as it is possible that multiple actions are needed for a single DQI. For each activity, a deadline and a responsibility need to be indicated, to guarantee that the action will be taken into account and it will be concluded.

<i>Improvement activity</i>	<i>Timeline</i>	<i>Responsible</i>	<i>Involved DQI</i>
<i>E.g.: Implement automatic measurements rejection if the measurement tool has not been calibrated in the last 4 times.</i>	<i>E.g.: 3 months (within June 2021)</i>	<i>E.g.: IT department</i>	<i>E.g.: Calibration vs measurements ratio</i>
<i>E.g.: Training of the volunteers</i>	<i>E.g.: 2 months (within May 2021)</i>	<i>E.g.: Pilot manager</i>	<i>E.g.: Volunteers' skill level measurement</i>

Table 6: Improvement activities table in DQA template

3.3 Process to explain and fill the template

As most of the pilots are not experts in data quality, the process was organized to guide them in filling the template. The proposed idea is to check if the pilot already analyzed possible causes of low data quality, in this case the first table (Ishikawa 6M) can be skipped. After this step, DQIs need to be defined, and it is necessary to check if there are goals missed. For each of them, at least an improvement activity needs to be set up.

Figure 3: Diagram to fill the DQA template

4 VALIDATION AND RESULTS

This chapter is divided into three main parts. At the beginning, it presents the validation methodology for the Data Quality process, used with pilots during the acceleration period, to guide them in the Data Quality assessment. The second paragraph describes in detail the analysis of the results collected with the Data Quality Assurance plans filled by pilots, including further guidelines to help in compiling the plan for future initiatives. Finally, in the third paragraph the results from the surveys filled by pilot managers are presented, including both data quality and data management questions.

4.1 Validation methodology

For the validation of the methodology two steps were planned: the first one is a process to improve the template together with pilots to analyze the usability of the tool, while the second one is a survey to evaluate the level of confidence with the topic of Data Quality, to understand the level of knowledge reached thanks to the Data Quality process.

For the process to improve the template, after the interactive session with a general overview on data quality, and a specific webinar on the template, the same pilots were invited in separate one-to-one calls to introduce the template. The purpose of the call was to better explain the functioning of the different tables, and to start to discuss together some possible examples inherent to the specific pilot.

After the call, the filling and review process started: a deadline was set up for each project, depending also on the specific timeline (just in case there is a document or a specific event coming soon which is better to wait before to fill the template). Once the template was filled out by the pilot, it was reviewed with the explanation of the necessary updates to be done and a new deadline. In some cases a single review was enough to finalize the document, while for some pilots a total of 5 or 6 different reviews were needed. It depends also on the complexity on how to ensure a good data quality, or on the level of expertise of the pilot managers. As the pilots are very different, in some cases they decided to fill a separate template depending on the type of activity implemented in the pilot, while in other cases some external evaluations of the quality of the data were attached, because an expert point of view was needed for specific topics.

During the filling phase, all the comments and possible questions on how to fill it were taken into consideration to understand how to better explain the activity. For a lot of the participants the main issues were related to how to take confidence with the dimensions (in order to choose the right one for the right problem), or to indicate the proper issues related to data quality, without going off topic. The results are described below in section 4.2 “Analysis of the collected templates from pilots”, together with the analysis and the summary of the contents collected.

About the creation of the survey, a list of questions were prepared to cover at least the most common dimension on data quality, starting as a basis from the questions asked for the impact assessment at the end of the first accelerator period, and reaching them to cover the needed dimensions. During the first interviews with pilots involved in the second round of the accelerator, a couple of questions were asked to the pilot managers to understand possible previous experience with similar projects (as respect to the accelerator pilot):

- Do you have previous experiences in Citizen Science projects?

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- If yes, is the data collection of your previous experience comparable with the one of [project name]? What are the main differences (e.g., presence or absence of data gathering instruments)?

In case the both questions were answered by a yes, the survey on data quality was provided twice: a first time at the beginning of the accelerator referring to the previous experience, and a second time at the end of the accelerator, together with questions on the impact assessment. Otherwise, if the pilot manager had no previous similar experiences, the replies to the survey were collected only at the end of the accelerator. Three projects also completed the ex-ante version, while the others completed only the ex-post. In appendix the complete list of questions.

4.2 Analysis of the collected templates from pilots

The results of the validation activity are reported below in three subsections reflecting the three tools provided.

4.2.1 Analysis of the Cause-Effect Diagrams

All the pilots filled the cause-effect diagram, in the form of a matrix as presented above. The summary of the low quality factors collected are reported for each of the 6Ms.

- **Man:** this was the most common problem in the Citizen Science initiatives, in mostly all the cases related to the volunteers involved in the data collection. In particular the main concerns were related to:
 - Volunteers skills: including mnemonic (e.g., ability to remember events to report), cognitive (e.g., ability to discriminate among soil colors), linguistic (e.g., ability to report in English for non-native speakers), and physical (e.g., the ability to reach remote places for specific measurements) skills.
 - Volunteers knowledge: including pre-acquired knowledge (e.g., digital literacy), domain specific knowledge (e.g., knowledge of the forest), and newly acquired knowledge (e.g., as a result of training activities).
 - Volunteers availability: both in terms of time, and availability in covering specific areas.
 - Volunteers training: volunteers' training is another frequently reported concern. For example, one initiative had issues with different training levels among participants, while another had problems in volunteers' understanding of the training instructions.
- **Machine:** this factor in Citizen Science initiatives was often related to physical equipment used during the measurement (indeed sometimes there are overlappings with the other "M"). More in general, three main types of "Machines" issues were found:
 - General equipment: few initiatives mentioned lab equipment or "sensors" in general as a source of potential errors in the collection of the data.
 - Mobile phones: many Citizen Science initiatives rely on volunteers' mobile phones, which might be critical in terms of: connection, battery duration, GPS precision, etc. In particular, many initiatives identified the mobile phone camera as potential sources of problems: picture quality (in terms of DPI), camera resolution (MegaPixels), camera performances in low light, fidelity of the colors, etc.
 - Software tools: some initiatives classified as a "machine" issue also non-physical tools, like cloud-based solutions or online surveys, where reliability is critical for proper data collection.

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- **Material:** Few initiatives reported problems related to materials, and in Citizen Science initiatives it was almost always related to toolkits provided to volunteers to participate in the data collection. This was due also to the fact that in many cases the volunteers' mobile phone was the only material needed. When mentioned, the toolkit issues were related to:
 - Toolkit availability: providing the toolkit to a large number of volunteers is not always trivial. In particular, during the COVID pandemic the reusability of the toolkits became a problem which limited the availability of toolkits (sanitation issues).
 - Toolkit clarity/ease of use: the more complex the toolkit use, the more it is a source of errors and problems. Especially when the toolkit is heavy to carry or takes space (for example, in an initiative the kit had to be carried on a boat, which usually has space constraints).
 - Toolkit perceived usefulness: if the volunteers don't see the toolkit as useful they are less prone to use it.
- **Method:** Most of the methods issues listed by the Citizen Science initiatives validating the methodology were related to the training process, while others had to do with how data are collected. In particular:
 - Training:
 - Training effectiveness: sometimes training programs fail to convey all the needed messages to trainees.
 - Training intensity: either in number of hours or in number of sessions.
 - Data collection:
 - Data collection accuracy: when the methodology with which the data is collected can impact on the final results.
 - Data collection harmonization: when combining data from different sources, errors might be introduced.
 - Data collection standardization: two initiatives listed standards (either internal standard or international standards) followed to improve data quality during the collection.
 - Data collection homogeneity: as different levels of understanding of project methodology among the participants might introduce discrepancies in the data.
- **Measurement:** many potential drawbacks for data quality were spotted by the Citizen Science pilots on the measurements, but most of them are related to the subjectivity of a measurement. In particular the full types of error sources were:
 - Subjectivity: as already mentioned, the subjective interpretation of the volunteers (or even experts) was the most common source of data quality issues.
 - Scales reliability: even if loosely linked to subjectivity, the lack of reliable scales is a factor on its own, which could potentially lead to less objective measurements, but that should be tackled in a different way.
 - Procedures/conditions: the measurement conditions (e.g., high levels of contamination compromising the reliability of the results) or procedures (e.g., temperature measured too rarely, or reading of a measurement instrument with high sun reflections, etc.) could compromise the quality of the data collected.
- **Mother Nature:** as many Citizen Science initiatives are related to environmental issues, in many cases the observations happen in natural environments (rivers, woods, etc.) which might be hardly accessible in case of bad weather conditions. Furthermore, force majeure

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issues were reported as well as “mother nature”, for example linked to COVID pandemic situations. In summary, the factors impacting on this M were:

- Weather conditions: for example excessive humidity, bad weather for walking in the woods, difficulties in assessing the soil color, difficulties in collecting water samples under the rain, sun during photo-documentation etc.
- Public health emergencies: especially because of COVID19, pilots had difficulties in collecting data in person, curfew, etc.
- Human factor: socio-political events, vandalism, etc.

All the most common causes for low data quality discovered during the work with the pilots has been summarized in the figure below, and can be used as a guiding checklist when filling the table presented in the section above about the cause-effect diagram.

Figure 4: Fishbone Diagram filled with the pilots information

4.2.2 Analysis of the Data Quality Indicators

The tables with Data Quality Indicators collected from the pilots were analyzed. The most relevant dimension is the **Completeness** (with 11 indicators defined and all the citizen science initiatives covering this dimension), with the **Accuracy** being the second (8 indicators defined, with all the initiatives covering this dimension), and **Consistency** being the third (with 9 indicators, but only 5 pilots out of 6 covering this dimension). Among the 5 main dimensions, **Timeliness** was covered by 50% of the initiatives, while **Accessibility** only by 1 initiative.

On the other hand, among the “secondary” dimensions listed, **Security** was mentioned by two initiatives (defining a total of 4 indicators) and **Understandability** by three initiatives (with three indicators in total).

The reason why Completeness, Accuracy and Consistency are the three most relevant dimensions might rely on the specificity of Citizen Science Initiatives, as in general there is an heterogeneous number of people (mostly volunteers) collecting data autonomously. The main risks are thus that data collection might be fragmented (consistency), that not all the volunteers have the same

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knowledge/skills/training (accuracy) and that data does not fully represent the coverage (frequently geographical coverage) of the phenomenon under observation (completeness).

In particular, analyzing each dimension:

- For **Completeness**, the indicators listed were mostly of three types:
 - Geographical coverage: meaning data from all the different areas/territories monitored in the initiative.
 - Task/observation completeness: meaning that the volunteers did thorough work in taking a measurement.
 - Number of functioning sensors/sampling stations: when there are deployed sensors.
- In **Accuracy**, most of the indicator were related to:
 - Equipment accuracy: either lab equipment or scale reliability.
 - Experts' acceptance of the data provided/classified by volunteers.
 - Instruments calibration.
- For **Timeliness**, all the indicators were related to the time frame, scale or resolution of the data collected.
- In the **Consistency** dimension, most of the pilots reported indicators related with volunteers' training and preparation. Some indicators in this dimension were also related to the consistency with expert teams or with official repositories/maps.

For the other dimensions, one or two indicators maximum were provided, so it is hard to generalize potential indicators. However, one interesting example is **Security**, for which both Citizen Science initiatives which covered it reported two indicators, with one being in common to both: compliance with GDPR. Citizen Science initiatives must take all the possible measures to ensure that no personal data (including geographical location in given moments) is ever revealed during the data collection process.

Methodologically, the test with the pilot initiatives provided two interesting insights. The first is that it is not always easy to correctly classify an indicator. One example is the indicator “percentage of homogeneous observations made by the research team”, which was classified as “Accuracy”, but it might very well be a “Consistency” indicator. However, methodologically this is not a major issue, as the goal of this activity is not indicator classification, but their definition. Once all the relevant indicators (with their respective goals) are in place for ensuring the quality of the collected results, it doesn't really matter to which dimension they belong to. Dimensions are to be intended as a wireframe for the indicator definition.

The second insight is that it is often hard to differentiate between data quality indicators and project results indicators. One example is the indicator “Percentage of findings about degraded soil”, defined by one pilot under the completeness dimension. Actually, the interpretation of the data (e.g., the soil being fertile or degraded) is not a data quality issue, in as far as the interpretation derives from data of a sufficient quality. In other words, data quality indicators must only ensure that the collected data is reliable and functional for its intended use. If the subsequent analysis reveals the existence or absence of a problem in a specific area, that is an indicator for the project's results. There is no strict rule to discriminate between project indicators and data quality indicators, but a good rule of thumb is to look for indicators which quantify data trustability/reliability. In borderline cases like the one listed above, a suggestion is to determine whether failing to reach the indicator's goal compromises the possibility to use the data in the intended evaluations (in which case it is a data quality indicator) or not. If data can be used anyway

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(independently from the fact that it supports or hinders the ongoing initiative), that is a project indicator and not a data quality indicator.

4.2.3 Analysis of the Improvement Activities

The improvement activities provided by the pilot initiatives were analyzed as well to gather further possible lessons learnt and guidelines in the creation of high quality data. One important preamble is that most of these pilots were interviewed at an early stage of their initiative, thus many of the most common issues might be related to the set-up or start-up of the initiatives. However, many considerations are good also for more mature projects.

Even if many improvement actions are specific for the various projects, below we report a generalization of the most common ones, sorted by occurrence:

- **Improvement in the training of the volunteers:** this is by far the action which was more recurrent, sometimes with several different actions in the same initiative. This can be related to the improvement of the training sessions, the training materials, the frequency of the training, etc. This class of improvement action was mentioned by 4 pilots out of 6, with one of them defining 8 actions for improving the training.
- **Improve sensors or toolkits' manuals, quality, accessibility (e.g., language barrier) and maintenance:** sensors and toolkits (in general "tools") play a fundamental role in getting high quality data, as they are in many cases the source of the data to be collected. Some of these tools require constant maintenance (recharging, updating, upgrading, etc.), and in general they must be kept as accessible and usable as possible. For this reason some pilots planned to improve their usability, their manuals or the translation of the tools in a local language.
- **Constant review of data acquisition activity:** besides training and tools quality, one of the main improvement actions class was related to the review of the data acquired in the field, both from volunteers and by the project team. Sometimes this review includes the involvement of experts or the comparison of data generated by experts.
- **Improve internal communication:** this action was mentioned by 50% of the pilots, meaning that it has quite a relevance in Citizen Science initiatives. With internal communication they meant among the initiative coordinators, between coordinators and volunteers and among volunteers. One pilot created a Telegram group to provide a channel for all the volunteers to communicate.
- **Integration of activities from different volunteers:** this improvement action was designed by three different pilots, with very different goals and DQIs. In general this action is meant for leveraging on group work to reduce individual errors or for cross-check, but one pilot designed it also to integrate volunteers with different skills (e.g., knowledge of the woods and technical skills).
- **Increase activity in uncovered areas:** even if mentioned only by two pilots, this is an important action to keep in mind, especially for ensuring geographical coverage and data completeness.

Further actions were mentioned by single pilots only, but are worth mentioning:

- **Gather feedback from participants:** which might be a good strategy to further investigate struggles of participants either in participating in data collection activities or to provide quality data.
- **Create a plan for data sampling:** this is particularly useful when the timing of the measurement is important, to ensure constant data update from relevant areas.

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- **Creation of a data quality scale:** this action could help in those cases in which data quality is rather subjective and difficult to assess otherwise.
- **Improve external outreach/communication:** similar to internal communication, which was instead a major improvement, the external communication could improve both the impact of the initiative and the enrollment of further contributors/volunteers.
- **Creation of a help desk:** to further support volunteers in the struggles of data collection.
- **Increase the number of sensors:** when economically sustainable, this is an action that could improve the data quantity or resolution.
- **Increase the involvement of experts:** when available, experts play a fundamental role in Citizen Science initiatives, from the training of the volunteers up to the validation of the data collected.
- **Compare the data with existing references:** when there are already existing and available databases overlapping with or comparable to the data gathered by the Citizen Science initiative, this action could be a first validation of the quality of the collection.
- **Improve compliance with regulations:** this action was mentioned by one pilot which set the compliance with the GDPR as a DQI.

4.3 Survey results analysis

The involved pilots filled a survey to assess different aspects of data management in their pilots. As described in the validation methodology, some of them also received an ex-ante survey with the same questions, in order to collect the same information from previous experiences (where applicable), related to past projects that can be compared to the ones running during the accelerator. There were 3 replies for the ex-ante evaluation, and 6 for the accelerated pilots. In the following discussion the term ex-ante refers to the questionnaires filled on previous similar projects, while the ex-post are the sub-group related to the accelerated projects, who had also similar previous experiences (who also filled the ex-ante). The label “All” indicates all the questionnaires related to the accelerated projects (both the ones with previous experiences, and the ones at the first experience).

The questionnaire is divided mainly in three parts: the first is related to data quality, the second to the openness of the data, and the third is specific to the fairness. Furthermore, in the ex-ante version a specific question asking to describe the previous project experience was included at the beginning, while a dedicated question about ACTION support on data quality, and a question on how the pilots set up their own data quality strategy were inserted in the questionnaire filled at the end of the accelerator. The administration of this last questionnaire is also part of the impact assessment. In this document there is only the analysis of the aggregated information compared with the ex ante replies, while in D6.4 further details on specific pilots are provided.

4.3.1 Data quality

In the questionnaire provided to pilots, the eight questions related to the data quality cover different aspects, but as the projects are very different, each one could have different levels of importance, depending on the project, with the consequence that addressing it could be more or less urgent. The list of questions is represented in the following table:

Q1	To what extent is there a procedure for adapting the process of data collection based on feedback, before data collection is fully rolled out?
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Q2	To what extent are the tasks for the volunteers easy?
Q3	To what extent have volunteers been given appropriate training?
Q4	To what extent are task procedures and data entry systematic, for example by devising data-entry procedures for volunteers to follow, or forced field-types for online data-entry?
Q5	To what extent is the equipment used for measurements standardized and calibrated across volunteers?
Q6	To what extent does the project record relevant metadata?
Q7	To what extent are the data complete, for example in terms of full geographical coverage, full population observation, sufficient time resolution, etc., rather than only partial data?
Q8	To what extent does your data provide an updated picture of the phenomenon you are observing (rather than e.g. outdated data)?

Table 7: Data Quality closed questions asked to pilots

A summary of the replies are represented in the diagram below, where it is possible to compare the average (based on increasing scores from 1 to 5) of all the answers for ex-ante questionnaires, ex-post, or the global replies after the end of the acceleration period (the ones included in the ex-post together with the replies from those who didn't have previous experiences in this field).

Figure 5: Data Quality replies

The first question (Q1) is related to the procedures implemented for data collection: *“To what extent is there a procedure for adapting the process of data collection based on feedback, before data collection is fully rolled out?”*. It is possible to see from the diagram that the pilots who already experimented with a similar project increased their evaluation by half a point (from 2.5 to 3, value reached in the ex post), while in general at the end of the accelerator the score is 2.6. It could be due to a slow down of the procedure implementation for pilot managers who never experienced similar situations.

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The easiness of the assigned tasks was investigated in the second question (Q2): *“To what extent are the tasks for the volunteers easy?”*. It is important to guarantee a task that could be done by all volunteers, and the average score for all the columns is 3. This is likely due to the need to balance the requests for the volunteers, with something that could be easy to be done. Furthermore, in a specific case a pilot had the first experience (ex-ante) with experts, while the second one is with normal citizens (ex-post and all). This example could affect the results, because of course in the first project the tasks were perceived as easier than in the second one, due to the expertise of the people recruited.

Another important aspect in citizen science pilots that could affect data quality is the training. The third question (Q3) investigates it: *“To what extent have volunteers been given appropriate training?”*. In this case the bars on the graph show that not only the project with previous experiences increased their average of training, but also the global score is higher than the ex-post (ex-ante 4, ex-post 4.2, all 4.3). The fact that this is one of the most important aspects for all pilots helps to increase these averages, but also the accelerator support could have increased these results, especially for pilots without experience.

Question 4 (Q4) is about data-entry: *“To what extent are task procedures and data entry systematic, for example by devising data-entry procedures for volunteers to follow, or forced field-types for online data-entry?”*. From the data collected, it emerges a 4 as average for the ex-ante replies, a 3.7 for the ex-post and a 4.2 for the final surveys. This decrease of average between ex-ante and ex-post is due to a pilot who enrolled people who are not very skilled with technologies, during the accelerator period. The consequence is that the pilot managers inserted by themselves the data collected by volunteers into the system, which is a step back with respect to the previous experience of citizen science. Apart from this exception, all pilots scored this question with a 4 or a 5, which means that this aspect is considered very important by all projects.

The following question is about the equipment (Q5): *“To what extent is the equipment used for measurements standardized and calibrated across volunteers?”*. This is an aspect strongly related to the type of pilot: for some of them it is crucial, for some others it is not applicable, because they don't use particular equipment, or maybe the volunteers use just their own smartphone (in this case a low score was assigned because calibration on personal devices is not so easy to perform). This aspect affected mostly the pilots involved in the accelerator, which is why the average scores are 3.7 for the ex-ante, 2.5 for the ex-post and 3.3 for the accelerated pilots.

Another important aspect for data quality is related to metadata, which is mentioned in the sixth question (Q6) *“To what extent does the project record relevant metadata?”*. In this case there is a good increase from ex-ante to ex-post score (from 2.7 to 3.7) while the global score of the accelerated pilot is lower than the separated group of the ex-post (3.2). This is due to a pilot that didn't fill the ex-ante survey, and didn't collect metadata, because for its purpose it needs only complete and very detailed information. This score decreased the average of the “all” label, for question 6.

In question 7 (Q7) the data completeness is investigated, asking *“To what extent are the data complete, for example in terms of full geographical coverage, full population observation, sufficient time resolution, etc., rather than only partial data?”*. This score was affected by the short timing of the accelerator, which in some cases doesn't allow a full acquisition as expected by the project (caused also by internal delays). The different averages are 3.7 for the ex-ante, 3.3 for the ex-post and 3.4 for all the accelerated projects.

It is important for a citizen science pilot to check if the collected information are able to reflect the actual situation of the observed phenomenon, as asked in question 8 (Q8): *“To what extent does your data provide an updated picture of the phenomenon you are observing (rather than e.g.*

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outdated data)?”. The averages are encouraging, because from the ex-ante to ex-post there was an increase of the value (from 3.3 to 4), while the global average for the accelerated pilots is 3.8. This last value is lower than the ex-post because there was a pilot at the first experience who had delays in starting the data collection, without reaching a satisfying representation during the accelerator lifetime.

Finally, at the end of the accelerator two more questions were asked to the pilot managers. The first is about their need to develop a method to ensure high quality data: *“Would you like to elaborate on your methods for ensuring high quality data?”*. Most of the pilots replied that they set up their own method thanks also to the Data Quality Assurance plan, made during the accelerator period. The second question was about the efficacy of the data quality training during the ACTION accelerator: *“What, if anything, did you learn from your participation and training during ACTION in terms of data quality? For example, did you change your data collection methods?”*. Also in this case, most of the pilots appreciated the support provided by ACTION. For some of them it was a good chance to reflect about data quality assurance, and the indicators provided helped to reflect on possible issues and how to solve them. Furthermore, the focus on the importance to properly engage citizens with effective training, or to follow standardized procedures and protocol raised. In one case, the pilot was already following standard procedure due to an external subcontractor which set up the data quality plan at the beginning of the project. Anyway, the manager considered ACTION training very helpful and he appreciated the knowledge acquired during the process.

4.3.2 Openness of data

Openness of data is crucial for citizen science projects, because, to guarantee adequate success, data and results should be available and disseminated as much as possible. To measure this aspect, a checklist of five Yes/No question was provided:

Are the data available on the web (whatever format) with an open license, to be Open Data?
Are the data available as machine-readable structured data (e.g. excel instead of image scan of a table)?
Are the data published in a non-proprietary format (e.g. CSV instead of excel)?
Does your data follow best practices for open data from W3C or another source?
Do the data link to other people’s data(sets) to provide context?

Table 8: Yes/no checklist to investigate if data are open

To analyse the results, the replies were divided with the same approach of the previous questions: a group related to the ex-ante surveys, a group for the final survey at the end of the accelerator (all) and a sub-group of this last one category, with the final answers from the pilot who filled also the ex-ante survey (ex-post group). The replies are presented by percentages of yes and no obtained for each category:

Figure 6: Openness of data replies

From the diagram, it is possible to see that the ex-post results have more “yes” than the other two groups (92%, where the ex-ante has 50% and all 74%). It is good to see that compared with previous experiences, during the accelerator, pilots were organized in order to reach a higher openness of the data.

4.3.3 FAIRness

FAIR principles² are increasingly mentioned when speaking about data. This is why pilots were asked to score from 1 to 5 to what extent they consider their data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. In the table below there are the averages of the replies for the four principles.

Figure 7: Fairness of data replies

For all of them, there is an increase with respect to the ex-ante average, both for the ex-post and for the “all” category. Mostly, the ex-post is the highest, which could be due to knowledge gained in the previous experience. However, also the “all” group has a higher score than the ex-ante,

² <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

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probably because starting with the accelerator instead of an isolated experience provides more information and materials to be aligned with FAIR principles.

5 PRACTICAL CASE: STREET SPECTRA

Street Spectra is a citizen science project to map and characterize public lighting sources. Volunteers use a low cost diffraction grating on top of their smartphones' camera to take pictures of the street lamps and their emission spectra.

Images are collected using the application Epicollect. In Addition to images, citizens collect other kinds of information such as *datetime*, *location* and *type of lamp*. The first two parameters are provided by the application, while the third is provided by the citizen. The project has written a tutorial to help citizens to identify lamp spectra.

To improve the quality of the image, this tutorial describes the process to take a valid image. In this case, citizens must be placed close to the lamppost, capture the light source together with the spectre and rotate the grating 45 degrees. Also, it is recommended to activate the auto mode in your mobile phone. Next figure shows an example of an image taken with Epicollect.

Figure 8. Image taken with Epicollect5

As it has been commented, citizens can add an observation about the identification of the spectre generated by the lamp. To improve the data of this attribute, the images are uploaded to a specific project in the Zooniverse platform³. This platform allows crowdsourced projects where citizens can contribute, adding more observations over images (or other multimedia files). In this case, citizens

³ <https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/actionprojecteu/street-spectra>

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can select the light source, draw a rectangle on the spectre, and identify the type of lamp (led, hps, etc.).

Figure 9. Image classified with Zooniverse

At this point, the project has a database of images labelled. To get the definitive results, all these data must be processed, applying two algorithms:

- Because citizens can upload images freely, it can happen that the project has two images of the same lamppost. Thus, it is necessary to calculate if both images refer to the same lamppost. An algorithm based on the location is applied to do it.
- The system is programmed to accept five observations over an image. As a result, the final response must be calculated to reach a consensus. The statistic selected to measure this consensus is *Fleiss' kappa*.

In summary, to assure the quality of the data generated in this project, we have combined tutorials to train citizens in order to collect data effectively, with algorithms to reconcile different observations based on locations and the contribution of the citizens.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Achieving satisfactory data quality is a non-trivial challenge in many domains, and it is particularly difficult in Citizen Science initiatives, in which often the resources allocated to a proper infrastructure for data collection and training of volunteers are limited.

The goal of this deliverable is to provide some concrete tools that can be used to assess the data quality of a Citizen Science initiative. These tools support a cause-effect analysis (of poor data quality) to identify the main potential issues in data collection, a methodology to define concrete and measurable data quality indicators based on the main relevant quality dimensions, and a structure for the definition of data quality improvement activities.

These templates were tested in existing Citizen Science initiatives, which piloted their use and provided already a list of the main findings with respect to causes of low quality, main relevant dimensions/indicators, and main improvement activities.

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These lessons learnt can be used as further guidelines for the improvement of other initiatives, both in the planning and execution phase.

The proposed tools were applied successfully by all the pilot initiatives, with just a minor initial training related to their use and application.

Some additional considerations could be made related to the timing in the use of these tools. All the ACTION pilots lasted 6 months, and many of them did not have an actual database or pre-existing information before starting their initiative. This makes it very hard to make an assessment of the collected data quality before the pilot starts, but on the other hand it poses a risk of an a posteriori analysis which identifies potential issues too late. For this reason, the optimal timeline for the application of the tools is:

- Creating a draft before the beginning of the project (especially the template related to cause-effect diagram)
- Start a “sampling” period of 1-2 months
- Make the full analysis after the initial sampling period to identify all the potential issues and correct them within the initiative lifetime.

A final consideration is related to the difference between data quality and project outcomes. Many pilots had difficulties in differentiating between satisfactory data quality and satisfactory outcomes described by the data. All the guidelines and considerations included in this deliverable are related only to the improvement of the data quality, which might have a positive effect on project outcomes (or dissemination), but this is not implicit.

6 APPENDICES

Data quality questionnaire

CS managers

Please fill this questionnaire thinking about your previous comparable experiences in CS projects. Do not refer to your running project under acceleration, this will be evaluated at the end of the period. (only for the ex-ante)

Could you briefly describe your previous project? *(it was asked only for the ex ante)*

Quality of the data

1. To what extent was there a procedure for adapting the process of data collection based on feedback, before data collection was fully rolled out? This could be done by iterative design, using one or more rounds of pilot or Beta testing and ensures that volunteers and/or sensors could perform the data collection without confusion or errors.

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

2. To what extent were the tasks for the volunteers easy?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

3. To what extent have volunteers been given appropriate training?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

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4. To what extent were task procedures and data entry systematic, for example by devising data-entry procedures for volunteers to follow, or forced field-types for online data-entry?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

5. To what extent was the equipment used for measurements standardized and calibrated across volunteers?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

6. To what extent did the project record relevant metadata?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

7. To what extent were the data *complete*, for example in terms of full geographical coverage, full population observation, sufficient time resolution, etc., rather than only partial data?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

8. To what extent did your data provide an updated picture of the phenomenon you were observing (rather than e.g. outdated data)?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

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Would you like to elaborate on your methods for ensuring high quality data? *(it was asked only at the end of the accelerator period)*

What, if anything, did you learn from your participation and training during ACTION in terms of data quality? For example, did you change your data collection methods? *(it was asked only at the end of the accelerator period)*

Openness of data

The following five questions are based on a 5 star rating scheme for Open Data and on the FAIR principles.

9. Were the data available on the web (whatever format) with an open license, to be Open Data?

- Yes, please specify where:
- No
- Not applicable

10. Were the data available as machine-readable structured data (e.g. excel instead of image scan of a table)?

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

11. Were the data published in a non-proprietary format (e.g. CSV instead of excel)?

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

12. Did your data follow best practices for open data from W3C or another source?

- Yes, please describe source:
- No
- Not applicable

13. Did the data link to other people's data(sets) to provide context?

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

Fairness

14. To what extent do you consider your data easily Findable?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

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15. To what extent do you consider your data Accessible?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

16. To what extent do you consider your data Interoperable?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

17. To what extent do you consider your data Reusable?

Please indicate on a scale from 1-5, where 1=not at all, and 5=a lot.

1 2 3 4 5

b. If you scored 3 or higher, please describe how:

For the ex-post questionnaire, the questions are the same but referred to the actual project.

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